

Research Article

Heuristic Approach to Palliative Measures and Its Resultant Impact on
COVID - 19 Pandemic in Nigeria

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Abstract

The state of insecurity in Nigeria, lack of social welfare programme and poor management of the palliatives has eroded public confidence in the government at various levels. The lockdown as a result of the outbreak subjected people to economic hardships, people had little to rely on and citizens living in poverty did not have welfare relief that could help them cope with the economic hardship at the time. In this paper, COVID 19 cases and its impacts on food prices is examined using the data from the daily COVID-19 cases update released by the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) online database from February 28th, 2020 – 31st August 2020 and food prices. The effect of the pandemic had a negative impact on food security with increase in food prices and food shortages.

Keywords: Palliative, food security, COVID-19, centre for disease control, basic food staples, Nigeria.

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Introduction

The origin of corona virus was traced to Wuhan, Hubei Province, China where residents who lived in Wuhan had some link to a large seafood and live animal market. The transmission of corona virus was zoonotic. The virus has been named "SARS-CoV-2" and the disease it causes has been named "corona virus disease 2019" (with the acronym "Covid-19"). The first known patient of Corona virus started experiencing symptoms in Wuhan, China on

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1 December 2019(Ozili 2020
<https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/#countries>).

COVID-19 was confirmed in Nigeria on 27th February 2020 through an infected Italian citizen who came in contact with a Nigerian citizen who was subsequently infected with the corona virus. The corona virus then spread to other citizens in Lagos and to other parts of the country (www.covid19.ncdc.gov.ng). The reported cases in Nigeria as at 30/8/2020 indicated that 405,916 samples were tested with confirmed cases of 54,008 which affected all the states in Nigeria including Federal Capital Territory, FCT. The discharged, admitted and deaths were 41,638, 11,357 and 1,013(Table 1). From Table 1 it showed that Lagos State had the highest number of cases because it was first reported there while Kogi State had the lowest case in Nigeria. The global total was 25,118,689 confirmed cases with 844,312 deaths in 216 countries and territories of the world. Demographic analysis revealed that 64% were males with 34,326 cases while the females were 19,682 accounting for 36%. The most affected age group are those within 31 - 40 (25%). Provenance travel history - 850 (1%) contacts - 12,778 (24%) and unknown exposure of 40,380 (75%) (www.covid19.ncdc.gov.ng). It is feared that the World may experience global economic recession because of uncertainty and fear among investors to invest during the pandemic which would affect firms' profit. Pandemic and epidemic outbreaks related to animals were reported to affect food security which were traced to the first poultry disease- Avian influenza (1878); the Newcastle disease (1926) and highly pathogenic avian influenza subtype H5N1 of 1997 (Reperant and Osterhaus, 2017; Ozili, 2020).

The restriction of movement imposed by both the State and Federal governments to reduce the spread of corona virus has affected virtually all sectors of the Nigerian economy. There was depression in banks earnings and the national budget which was initially predicated on \$57 per barrel was reduced to \$30 per barrel. Pharmaceutical supplies, spare parts, and finished goods and the lost over ₦2.3 trillion (US\$5.9bn) in the Nigerian stock market were reported barely three weeks after the first case of corona virus was confirmed and announced in the country.

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Table 1: COVID-19 Cases in Nigeria as at 31/8/2020

States	Total	Discharge	Deaths	Admitted
Lagos	18,138	15,231	202	2,705
FCT	5,169	1,536	50	3,583
Oyo	3,118	1,954	37	1,127
Edo	2,584	2,325	100	159
Plateau	2,533	1,395	29	1,109
Kaduna	2,141	1,991	12	138
Rivers	2,141	1,971	57	113
Delta	1,744	1,540	47	157
Kano	1,727	1,537	54	136
Ogun	1,648	1,515	26	107
Ondo	1,539	1,380	31	128
Enugu	1,162	907	21	234
Ebonyi	993	931	27	35
Kwara	966	784	25	157
Katsina	796	457	24	315
Osun	782	734	17	31
Abia	771	697	8	66
Borno	741	671	36	34
Gombe	723	636	23	64
Bauchi	667	581	14	72
Imo	527	193	11	323
Benue	453	216	9	228
Nasarawa	434	298	12	124
Bayelsa	391	348	21	22
Jigawa	322	308	11	3
Akwa Ibom	278	232	8	38
Ekiti	262	203	4	55
Niger	243	216	12	15
Adamawa	228	180	15	33
Anambra	216	168	18	30
Sokoto	159	140	16	3
Kebbi	93	82	8	3
Taraba	87	73	5	9
Cross River	82	73	8	1
Zamfara	78	73	5	0
Yobe	67	59	8	0
Kogi	5	3	2	0
	54,008	41,638,	1,013	11,357

Source: www.covid19.ncdc.gov.ng

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The United Nations World Food Programme has estimated that about 265 million people could be impacted by food insecurity in 2020; this is an increase of 96% compared to 135 million who experienced food insecurity before the crisis. The overall impact of the conflict on agriculture is estimated at about USD 3.7 billion (World Food Programme, 2020).

Hand washing protocol, personal hygiene, use of alcohol-based hand sanitizers, avoiding touching the eyes, nose, mouth, avoiding crowds, avoiding unnecessary outings and travels, use of face masks among other WHO recommended protocols, including coughing protocol and physical distancing were the measures adopted for COVID-19 infection and spread (Forsido *et al.*, 2020). Food and nutrition security, disruption of food supply chains, hindrance of farmers from accessing their farms in other state locations or procuring inputs such as seedlings and farm implements, post-harvest losses and disruptions in household income are some of the consequences of the lockdown. George (2020) reported uncertainties in the coping strategies of households as a result of the measures adopted for the containment of the pandemic. During the outbreak, people had little to rely on; Nigerian citizens living in poverty do not have welfare relief that could help them cope with the economic hardship during the pandemic as there were no subsidies for energy and utilities and assistance for other basic services to individuals that were most affected by the corona virus outbreak. The pandemic adversely affected food security in the area of shortage in food supplies, disruption of economic activities and the inability of industries that rely on food importation to thrive.

In order to cushion the effects of the pandemic, governments in developed countries like U.S.A and U.K provided fiscal stimulus package including social welfare payments to citizens while the monetary authorities offered loan relief to help businesses during the pandemic. In an effort to mitigating the spread of the pandemic, monetary and fiscal policy measures were equally adopted in response to the pandemic in response to the COVID-19 outbreak in Nigeria. The palliative measures included extension of loan moratorium on principal repayments, interest rate reduction on all intervention loan facilities from 9% to 5% beginning from March 1, 2020, offered a ₦50 billion (US\$131.6m) targeted credit facility to hotels, airline service providers, health care merchants, among others and provided credit support to the healthcare industry to meet the increasing demand for healthcare services during the outbreak. The Federal Government made provision for cash transfers of ₦20,000 (about \$51.75) to vulnerable households, which is infinitesimal insignificant considering the number of people living in poverty in Nigeria which is very is on the high side and

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many people will likely miss out on these transfers (Aref-Adib, 2020). Nigeria is reported to be the world centre of poverty in spite of her huge revenue from oil.

The broad objective of the paper is Heuristic Approach to Palliative Measures and Its Resultant Impact on COVID - 19 Pandemic in Nigeria with the specific objective of examining the impact of the pandemic on prices of selected basic food staples in the country.

Methodology

Data for the study were obtained from the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) online database (www.covid19.ncdc.gov.ng) from February 28th, 2020 - August 31st, 2020. The data were on total deaths, admitted cases, discharged cases and total number of COVID-19 cases as released by NCDC. National Food Prices from January 2019 to August 2020 were also obtained from National Bureau of Statistics.

Methods of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were employed in the analysis of the data collected. Mean, standard deviation, tables and percentages were the descriptive statistics used to examine the nature of the data. Inferential statistics (T- test statistic) was used to examine the impact of COVID-19 Cases on food prices. T - test statistics was used to examine the impact of COVID- 19 on food prices is expressed as:

$$T = \frac{y_a - y_b}{\sqrt{\frac{na}{sa} + \frac{nb}{sb}}}$$

Where: y_a = mean food price before COVID19, y_b = mean food prices during COVID 19, S_a = standard error of food price before COVID19, S_b = Standard error of food price during COVID 19, n_a = number of basic food items before COVID19 and n_b = number of basic food items

Results and Discussion

Summary statistics of COVID-19 Cases

Analysis in Table 2 shows that the mean of total deaths was 27 and a standard deviation of 35.30136 while the minimum and maximum deaths were 2 and 202. The minimum and maximum confirmed cases were 5 and 18, 138 with the mean and standard deviation of 1,460 and 3017.904. The mean and

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standard deviation of the admitted cases of COVID-19 were 307 and 739.211. The maximum number of cases on admission was 3,583 whereas the mean of discharged cases was 1,125 with standard deviation of 2,476.58. From the analysis, one can infer that admitted cases and discharged cases are the indicators that can flatten the curve of COVID-19 cases thereby reducing the number of related deaths in Nigeria.

Table2: Summary of Descriptive Statistics of COVID-19 cases in Nigeria

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Total deaths	27.37838	35.30136	2	202
Confirmed cases	1459.676	3017.904	5	18138
Admitted cases	306.9459	739.211	0	3583
Discharged cases	1125.351	2476.58	3	15231

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2020 using STATA Version 11

Impacts on Food prices

Table 3 shows major food items and their prices before and during the COVID-19 Cases in Nigeria. Beans brown, sold loose; beans and white black eye sold loose where the only two of the food items that had reduction in their prices while the remaining 16 basic food recorded price hikes. These food items are basic energy food requirements of 2,100 kilocalories per person per day. The overall increase in selected basic food staples in the country was 15.88 %. Furthermore, the t-test statistic also revealed that COVID-19 had a significant impact on food prices at 5% level (Table 4). The result is in agreement with Swinnen and MC Dermot (2020) who reported disruption in food supply because of the lockdown which restricts movement of labour and food items causing increases in food and further aggravating food security situations among the people living in poverty in many developing countries of the world. People who earn livelihood and incomes from food business (transportation, marketing, value addition) would be displaced. Amare *et al.*(2020) also reported increases food prices in the country as a result of COVID-19.

The Agricultural Promotion Policy (APP) introduced by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD) considers food as a human right in her food policy document - focusing the policy instruments for agricultural development on the social responsibility of government with respect to food security, social security and equity in the Nigerian society; and compelling the government to recognize, protect and fulfil the freedom of the

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people from hunger and malnutrition. Good as the policy on food security appears, it would not make any impact without any commitment on the part of the government to provide the enabling environment for major stakeholders to operate. The inability of the Nigerian government to curtail security challenges facing most parts of the country especially the northern part fraught with armed banditry, insurgency, farmer- herder clashes with high number of internally displaced persons in camps with limited food supplies with limited incomes are adversely affected. Their livelihood activities are affected and may not have access to humanitarian services rendered NGOs. Food production is a critical component of food security, but because of security challenges, farmers abandoned their farms as not only farm produce are destroyed by herders, but they are mostly maimed or killed or kidnapped by armed bandits. Malnutrition is widespread in the entire country and rural areas especially vulnerable chronic food shortages with differences in geo political zones: 56% (south west) and 84.3% (northern Nigeria).The country is still characterized by high reliance on food imports due to challenges of adverse weather conditions associated with climate change, herder-farmer clashes, terrorism in the northeast, cattle rustling, low levels of mechanization, and poor research and development activities. To bridge the demand-supply gap brought about by low agricultural productivity, the country imports agricultural products such as wheat, palm oil, etc. In four years (2016-2019), Nigeria's cumulative agricultural imports stood at N3.3 trillion, four times more than the country's agricultural exports of N803 billion in the same period. The rate of population growth outstripped the rate of food production. The results of the government's policies to reposition the agricultural sector have been mixed. The Agricultural Promotion Policy (APP) introduced by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD) with various intervention programmes by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) such as the Anchor Borrowers Programme, have led to transformation in the rice production but the policies score recorded poor performance in the attainment of self-sufficiency for key agricultural products. For example, annual wheat production which stands at 0.06 million metric tonnes is barely able to cover local demand of over 5 million metrics tonnes despite the APP setting 2018 as the target year in which the nation would have attained self-sufficiency in wheat production. Wheat dominates Nigeria's agricultural imports and accounted for about 40.7% (or N390.6 billion) in 2019.

With COVID-19, the challenges hampering the attainment of food security in Nigeria had deepened as shown by increases in the cost of the basic food items. The impact is already being felt in the form of rising food prices. The recent withdrawal of subsidies on premium motor spirit and increase in

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Table 3: Pre COVID-19 and COVID-19 Food prices in Nigeria

Selected Food Items	Pre COVID-19 Price (₦)	COVID-19 Price (₦)	Price Differential (₦)	Percentage
Beans brown,sold loose	355.0213	305.4343	-49.587	-13.96733
Beans:white black eye. sold loose	317.4413	274.8042	-42.6371	-13.43149
Broken Rice (Ofada)	377.0575	429.8098	+52.7523	+13.9905
Evaporated tinned milk carnation 170g	160.5113	162.2257	+1.7144	+1.06809
Evaporated tinned milk(peak), 170g	188.9525	194.1099	+5.1574	+2.72947
Gari white,sold loose	158.9975	224.5266	+65.5291	+41.2139
Gari yellow,sold loose	175.9713	253.0155	+77.0442	+43.7823
Groundnut oil: 1 bottle	570.9538	626.691	+55.7372	+9.76212
Maize grain white sold loose	147.2225	189.526	+42.3035	+28.7344
Maize grain yellow sold loose	150.6338	192.4348	+41.801	+27.7501
Palm oil: 1 bottle	460.085	499.6666	+39.5816	+8.60311
Rice agric sold loose	317.1763	413.1326	+95.9563	+30.2533
Rice local sold loose	278.2288	375.0798	+96.851	+34.8098
Rice Medium Grained	312.7775	415.4294	+102.652	+32.8195
Rice,imported high quality sold loose	359.6013	501.7088	+142.108	+39.5181
Tomato	240.3188	289.8631	+49.5443	+20.6161
Vegetable oil:1 bottle	500.2638	583.7588	+83.495	+16.6902
Wheat flour: prepacked (golden penny 2kg)	667.1238	718.3923	+51.2685	+7.68501
Grand total	5738.338	6649.609	911.2717	+15.88

Source: Authors' computation from NBS food prices 2020 + - denote increase and decrease in food price in Naira and percentages

electricity charges announced by the government had further worsened food security situation in the country. For example, the closure of borders by the government though to boost domestic food production was ill-timed as the country has no enough food supplies for her citizens as the food reserve silos are daily depleted by large number of people in internally displaced camps across the country. There was the release of 30,000 metric tonnes of grains from the strategic reserve of the country to the internally displaced people from various parts of the country.

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Another palliative measure was carried out by the government during the pandemic where additional 70, 000 metric tonnes were released to cushion the effect of the pandemic in addition to the contribution of Coalition Against COVID-19(CA COVID-19). The depletion of the country’s food reserves is faster than its replenishment because of low productivity of the agricultural sector as the low rate of replenishing the food reserve. Access to food is an integral component of food security because without the purchasing power people will be denied access to food items. A stable socio-economic and political environment at various levels of governance, national, state and local government level will guarantee production and food security. Famine Early Warning Systems Net (FEWSNET2020), FAO (2020) and World Food Programme (2020) reported food price increase in Nigeria was due to deteriorating macro economy and increase in pump prices petrol. For instance the increase in pump price has already triggered soaring transportation cost affecting the food supply chain in the country. The inability of the Nigerian government to have national social welfare programme became evident during the corona virus outbreak of 2020 as reported by Ozili (2020) who observed that during the outbreak, people had little to rely on and Nigerians living in poverty did not have welfare relief that could help them cope with the economic hardship. Ahmed et al. (2017) advocated the need for social welfare designed to meet the basic needs of the people.

The outbreak of COVID- 19 in Nigeria further aggravated the precarious and fragile food security in the country where there is no carefully planned welfare schemes for the country. The containment of the pandemic through lockdown imposed in the country resulted to the inability of the citizens to access the basic necessities of life especially food whose shortages will be more devastating than the COVID-19 itself because hunger will affect more in terms of population. The ENDSARS peaceful protest which later turned violent with the nationwide destruction of palliative stores across the country was a cumulative effect of bad governance, corruption and insensitivity on the part of the ruling class.

Table 4: T- test analysis of the impact of COVID-19 on Food prices

Variable	Mean Food price	Standard error	Mean dif	Df	T. value
Before COVID-19	318.79	152.93	50.63	17	12.03**
COVID-19 period	369.42	165.80			

Source: Authors’ computation, 2020. ** Significant at 5%

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Conclusion and Policy implication

There was significant impact on food price increase as a result of the pandemic. Government should formulate short, medium and long term policies for food production not only to cushion the effect of the pandemic but to fight hunger. Strategies such as the establishment of integrated, climate-smart production systems with food crops, cash crops and agro forestry should be put in place to enhance likelihood of the people in the country. Government should be proactive in the disbursement of incentives meant for her citizens.

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